

Article**Notes on the natural history of genus *Leptogenys* Roger, 1861 (Formicidae: Ponerinae) from India**PARVINDER SINGH BAIDWAN¹, HIMENDER BHARTI^{1*}¹Department of Zoology and Environmental Sciences, Punjabi University, Patiala, Punjab, 147002, India.

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The genus *Leptogenys* Roger, 1861 is distributed across tropical and subtropical regions worldwide, comprising over 334 valid species (Bolton, 2025). From India, 34 species have been reported (Bharti et al., 2016; AntWiki, 2025). Since *Leptogenys* is the most species-rich genus within the subfamily Ponerinae and its members display a variety of foraging patterns and reproductive systems that make it an ideal group for studying foraging and reproduction in the Ponerinae (Schmidt & Shattuck, 2014). Many species of the genus *Leptogenys* are specialist predators of specific prey, such as isopods, earwigs, earthworms, millipedes and termites (Wheeler, 1936; Maschwitz & Mühlenberg, 1975; Maschwitz & Schönegege, 1983; SteghausKovac & Maschwitz, 1993; Duncan & Crewe, 1994; Schmidt & Shattuck, 2014). The foraging behaviour of *leptogenys* species varies according to their prey preferences, from solitary foraging to mass raiding and group predation behaviour (Maschwitz et al., 1989; Dejean & Evraerts, 1997).

In this study, Cooperative hunting, scavenging and plesiobiosis were observed across *Leptogenys* species in multiple habitats in India. The images illustrating these behaviours were captured using a Nikon D5600 DSLR camera equipped with an 18-55mm kit lens. After recording their behaviour, the ants were collected in pure Merck ethanol for taxonomic study.

Cooperative hunting and chain formation behaviour of *Leptogenys processionalis* (Jerdon, 1851) and *Leptogenys diminuta* (Smith, F., 1857)

The observation was made in Ushakothi Wildlife Sanctuary, Odisha on 30th August 2021 (21°49'72" N, 84°29'11" E, 338m asl). The forest type was mostly dry deciduous, with frequent occurrences of floral species such as *Shorea robusta* (sal), *Santalum album* (sandalwood), *Terminalia arjuna* (Arjun), *Azadirachta indica* (neem), *Acacia* species and *Casuarina* species. Raiding workers of *Leptogenys processionalis* were observed moving in a single, uninterrupted queue, with one worker trailing behind the other. The centipede moved towards the opening of the nest. Initially few workers (scouts) approached the Centipede and touched the cuticle with their antennae. It is unknown if the ants can detect the pheromone of possible prey or if they come across them by accident. At initial contact the workers did not bite or sting but after 1–2 minutes, they encircled the centipede from every direction and used their powerful jaws and sting to capture and paralyze the centipede. Workers readily grabbed the prey with the help of their long, curved mandibles. After paralyzing the prey, workers started to form small chains and pull the prey toward the nest. However, the chains regularly broke and rebuilt, especially when encountered obstacles (fig. 1). Comparable behaviour was documented by Peeters & De Greef (2015) in Cambodia reported self-assembling chains in *Leptogenys* sp., where workers formed linear and branched chains to pull prey, sometimes involving up to 52 individuals.

A similar cooperative hunting strategy was also observed in *Leptogenys diminuta* at Shendurney Wildlife Sanctuary on 21st January 2023 (8°58'00"N 77°04'21"E, 176m asl) in the Kollam district of Kerala. During foraging, workers of *L. diminuta* encountered an Arachnid and exhibited aggressive predatory behaviour. Prey attempted to escape but was immobilized as workers firmly grasped its legs. Small chains were formed by workers, pulled the prey and marched toward the nest (fig. 2).

Scavenging behaviour of *Leptogenys processionalis* (Jerdon, 1851)

The scavenging behaviour of *Leptogenys processionalis* workers was observed from Insuli (Village in Sawantwadi Taluka in Sindhudurg District of Maharashtra State, India.) on 24th May, 2022. (15°50'04"N, 73°50'28"E, 28m asl). Workers were spotted emerging from house wall cracks and moving in a long queue, following one another and approaching the rat carcass. Using their powerful mandibles, they tore through the rat's skin. Chain-forming behaviour was not observed because the rat was too large for the workers to be pulled. Since rat skin was severely damaged, morphological identifications were not performed (fig. 3).

Figure 1. Cooperative hunting and chain formation behaviour of *Leptogenys processionalis* (Jerdon, 1851). **a)** Encircling of the centipede from every direction by the workers. **b)** Transportation of centipede into the nest by the workers.

Figure 2. Cooperating hunting and chain formation behaviour by *Leptogenys diminuta* (Smith, F., 1857) workers.

Figure 3. Scavenging behaviour of *Leptogenys processionalis* (Jerdon, 1851) on rat carcass.

Plesiobiosis between *Leptogenys dentilobis* (Forel, 1900) and *Camponotus angusticollis* (Jerdon, 1851)

Plesiobiosis was observed in Chimmony Wildlife Sanctuary, Kerala (10°25'28" N 76°29'20" E, 147m asl) on 15th January 2023. The sanctuary is situated on the Western slopes of the Nelliampathy Hills; forest-type is semi-evergreen to moist deciduous forest. Vegetation consists of Teak (*Tectona grandis*) plantation, *Palaquium ellipticum*, *Dipterocarpus indicus*, scrub and grass (Jayson, 1999). During fieldwork, nests of two different genera, *Leptogenys dentilobis* and *Camponotus angusticollis* were observed in close vicinity (separated by only a 3 cm distance) under the same stone. Several studies have reported plesiobiotic interaction of genus *Camponotus* with other species (Kanizsai et al., 2013). For the first time, we observed plesiobiotic interaction between *L. dentilobis* and *C. angusticollis*. Both have different patterns of foraging and feeding behaviour. *Leptogenys* shows group predation that prey on termites, millipedes, centipedes and spiders while *Camponotus* workers are omnivorous and consume insects, plant material and honeydew. If the species involved, have different resource preferences, different periods of activation, or separate foraging locations, then interspecific rivalry may be easier to avoid in these situations than intraspecific competition (Kanizsai et al., 2013). Nonetheless, certain ecological limitations appear to enable its occurrence, and data suggests that it could occur more frequently in habitats with high colony density and

little availability of suitable nest sites (Czechowski, 2004). So, the emergence of this connection can be due to strong intraspecific competition, high colony density and in scarcity of suitable nest sites. The co-existence between *Leptogenys dentilobis* and *Camponotus angusticollis* persisted as long as they remained undisturbed. However, upon the removal of the stone, both species came into direct contact, triggering aggressive interactions. A few workers engaged in fighting, while others started translocating their brood. (fig. 4).

Figure 4. a) *Leptogenys dentilobis* (Forel, 1900) b) *Camponotus angusticollis* (Jerdon, 1851) nests in close proximity under same stone (c) Pupae of *Leptogenys dentilobis* (d) Pupae of *Camponotus angusticollis*.

Such natural history observations are rarely documented and are important to record, as they provide valuable insights into species interactions, behavioural adaptations, and ecological dynamics.

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